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**Evaluation of the Prey Base and Feeding Relationships of the American Burying Beetle
(*Nicrophorus americanus*) on Nantucket Island**

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Abstract

The American burying beetle, *Nicrophorus americanus*, (ABB), once widely distributed across the eastern two-thirds of North America, has recently experienced a dramatic decline in abundance and geographic range. In 1989, the ABB was listed as a federally endangered species. The last recorded naturally occurring ABB on Nantucket Island, Massachusetts was in 1926. In 1994, efforts began to reestablish the ABB on Nantucket using lab-reared offspring of wild-caught individuals from Block Island, Rhode Island; the only naturally extant ABB population east of the Mississippi River. Despite an initially successful reintroduction, the population shows little evidence of recruitment and likely requires human assistance for long-term success. A key requirement of the ABB's life cycle is the availability of small vertebrate carcasses used for breeding. Despite over 30 years of research, we know little about the preferred carrion base necessary to support a healthy ABB population. In this study, we investigated feeding relationships of local burying beetles using stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) conducted on

small elytral clips collected from live-captured specimens. Because burying beetles build body tissues using nutrients from the carcass on which it was raised, the stable isotope ratios of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in adult burying beetles reflect their larval diet, indicating the carrion their parents used as a reproductive resource. We found a significant difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values among wild-caught burying beetle species. Additionally, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values differed significantly among wild-caught burying beetle species and potential carrion. This allows us to identify what small vertebrate species and the size of individual carrion used by *N. americanus* for reproduction. However, presently, our small samples sizes limit our interpretation of resources used by *N. americanus*, and other wild-caught burying beetle species.

Introduction

Nicrophorus americanus was once widely distributed across the eastern two-thirds of North America but has recently undergone a dramatic decline in its geographic range and abundance (Anderson 1982; Lomolino *et al.* 1995). Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain the species decline (Sikes and Raithel 2002), but it is likely that two of the primary factors leading to its endangered status are its relatively large size and specialized breeding behavior. Reintroduction attempts are underway or have been attempted in Ohio, Missouri and Massachusetts (on Nantucket Island).

The 2016 surveys on Nantucket resulted in the lowest number of captures in the 23 years of organized surveys (L. Perrotti pers. comm.). Despite a successful initial introduction to Nantucket, the population is not self-sustaining and may require human assistance for long-term maintenance (McKenna-Foster *et al.* 2016). Although *N. americanus* has been studied extensively relative to habitat use (Creighton *et al.* 1993; Lomolino *et al.* 1995; Bedick *et al.* 1999), its feeding relationships and availability of preferred food sources have never been quantified in a natural environment. Burying beetles use carrion for both nonreproductive feeding and for reproduction as food for their offspring. However, locating appropriate small vertebrate carcasses for breeding and raising offspring is more difficult than finding carrion on which to feed. Currently there is a lack of knowledge of which small vertebrate species and what size individuals are being used by *N. americanus* for reproduction, which challenges appropriate management of known *N. americanus* habitat. Thus, characterizing suitable habitat and

managing existing and reintroduced *N. americanus* populations depend on knowing the distribution and availability of all food sources. Furthermore, interspecific interactions among burying beetles can influence reproduction and establishment of reintroduced *N. americanus*. It is therefore important to understand interspecific interactions among members of the burying beetle community to better evaluate factors effecting population dynamics.

As stable isotope signatures of body tissues reflect the assimilated diet of the individual (Gannes et al. 1998; Zah et al. 2001; Ben-David and Flaherty 2012), they can provide quantitative information on resource use and width of the organisms' ecological niche (Newsome et al. 2007, Flaherty and Ben-David 2010, Eckrich et al. 2018). Additionally, when determine resource use and the width of an organism's ecological niche using stable isotope analysis, it is important to collect a variety of local, representative samples of potential food sources that are reflective of different dietary niches (Ben-David and Schell 2001, Phillips 2001, Flaherty et al. 2010). Because burying beetles grow and develop on a single food source (i.e. a single individual, small vertebrate) the body tissues of the adult beetles reflect the nitrogen-carbon isotopic signature of their larval food source, including the elytra (Gratton and Forbes 2006). Importantly, small samples of the elytra can be removed without affecting the survival of *N. americanus*. By employing stable isotope techniques will can determine the small vertebrate carrion base used as reproductive food resource for *N. americanus* and other locally abundant burying beetles in a natural environment.

Methods

Study Area

Pitfall trapping sites were located on the eastern side of the island (Fig. 1). We employed the same grid system used in previous years surveys from 2013 – 2016. Trap sites 2 and 13 were abandoned after 2013 and are not listed. The average distance between a site and its four closest neighbors is 1.96 ± 0.57 km. Assuming each trap line has an effective range of 0.8 km (USFWS 2013), the grid system covers 22.7 km².

Pitfall Trapping

We set traps on the night of 13 June 2017 and trapped continuously until 25 June 2017. Due to low trapping success, traps at site 1, 3, and 4 were closed 21 June, and we closed site 14 on 22 June. We placed 5 pitfall traps at all sights approximately 20 m apart in a straight line. We followed the ongoing trapping protocol originally described by Kozol (1991). Each pitfall trap consisted of a 946 ml mason jar buried with the top level to the soil. We placed a small plastic container with a screw-on mesh lid, which we filled with rotted chicken, inside of each pitfall trap. We prepared the chicken beforehand in plastic containers which we left at room temperature for 7-8 days prior to baiting the traps. We also placed a moist sponge in each trap to help prevent beetle desiccation. We covered each jar with a square piece of hardware cloth that we cut a 3 x 3 cm hole in the middle, this allowed beetles access to the trap and helped prevent other wildlife from disturbing them. We placed a disposable aluminum pan lid that we bent to resemble a “tent” over the pitfall trap and staked it down with ground staples to keep out rain and to provide shade. We checked traps every morning between 0600 and 1000 hr to ensure that all burying beetles were removed before traps became lethally warm. All *N. americanus* captured were collected in single occupancy containers to await provisioning, and a subset of the other burying beetle species captured were frozen until they were processed for analysis.

Field Sample Collection

We collected tissue for stable isotope analysis from 4 species of burying beetles (*N. americanus*, *N. orbicollis*, *N. tomentosus*, and *N. marginatus*; Table 1). To determine feeding relationships of *N. americanus*, we analyzed stable isotopes ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) using a small clip from the elytra of live-captured specimens; we used the whole elytra for all other burying beetle species. All samples for stable isotope analysis were collected during the peak reproductive season in mid-summer.

To compare to the signatures of the burying beetle species and determine carrion food sources, we collected whole blood and muscle tissue samples from locally available small mammals, and birds, (Table 2). We based the species sampled on small mammal and bird surveys previously conducted by Massachusetts Division of Fisheries and Wildlife. Most of these species range between 100-300 g (Schwartz and Schwartz 2001) and could provide a

suitable carrion base for *N. americanus*. The goal in our sampling was to represent variation in size and functional groups (e.g., herbivores versus insectivores) of the small vertebrate fauna.

Small mammal whole blood samples were collected by Danielle O'Dell using submandibular venipuncture, during her ongoing small mammal survey in July and September 2017. Avian whole blood samples were collected using brachial venipuncture. Mist netting for avian samples was facilitated by Dr. Richard Viet and Ginger Andrews on June 23rd. Additional muscle tissue samples (1-3 g) from mammals and birds were provided from frozen carcasses by the Maria Mitchell Association (Table 2).

None of the potential prey species collected were of conservation concern on Nantucket. All methods involving live vertebrates were approved by Purdue University's Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (PACUC # 1705001577) and followed recommendations by the Ornithological Council (Fair et al. 2010) and the American Society of Mammologists (Sikes et al. 2016).

Stable Isotope Sample Analysis

In the laboratory, all samples were dried at 60°C for 48 hr and then homogenized and ground into a fine powder using a mixer mill (Retsch MM 200, Glen Mills Inc., Clinton, NJ). Two subsamples (duplicates) were weighed to the nearest 0.01 mg (Sartoris CPA2P, Data Weighing Systems Inc., Elk Grove, IL) and placed in a miniature tin weigh boat (3 x 5 mm; Costech Analytical Technologies, Valencia, CA). All samples were sent to the University of Wyoming Stable Isotope Facility (University of Wyoming, Laramie, WY) for analysis of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ using an elemental analyzer and isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Thermo Finnigan Delta Plus XP, Costech 4010 and Carlo Erba 1110 Elemental Analyzer, Costec Zero Blank Autosampler, Finnigan Conflo III Interface).

Statistical analysis

We used a MANOVA and Tukey's HSD (Zar 2010) to evaluate and compare isotopic signatures among vertebrate prey. Based on these results, we categorized potential reproductive food resources (Brown rats, Mammals, Birds, Sea-birds, and Farm raised quail; Table 2.) Similarly,

we used a MANOVA (SAS Proc MIXED; SAS Institute 2000; Gratton and Forbes 2006) to assess differences in isotopic signature among species of burying beetles and potential prey. Due to a low sample size (n=1) we did not include *N. tomentosus* in our analysis.

Results

We found a significant difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values among different species of wild-caught burying beetles ($F_{(4,144)} = 8.82$; $p < 0.01$; Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.645$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.20$; Fig. 2). Values for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ differed significantly between wild-caught burying beetle species ($F_{(2,73)} = 17.77$; $p < 0.01$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.33$; and $F_{(2,73)} = 4.90$; $p < 0.01$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.12$; respectively). *Nicrophorus americanus* had significantly different $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$) than both *N. orbicollis* and *N. marginatus*. Conversely, we the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were only significantly different between *N. americanus* and *N. marginatus* (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$). However, we are limited in our interpretation between wild-caught burying beetle species due to a low sample size (Table 1).

Additionally, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values differed significantly among potential reproductive carrion ($F_{(8,210)} = 52.56$; $p < 0.01$; Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.111$; partial $\eta^2 = 0.67$; Fig. 2). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were significantly different between sea birds and all other potential reproductive carrion (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$), except farm raised quail (Tukey's HSD: $p = 0.071$). Values for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ between mammals and brown rats did not differ significantly (Tukey's HSD: $p = 1.00$). Additionally values for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ between and mammals and birds did not differ significantly (Tukey's HSD: $p = 0.362$), but they significantly differed between mammals and quail (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$; Tukey's HSD). Values for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in brown rats and birds were not significantly different (Tukey's HSD: $p = 0.911$). However, there was a significant difference between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values between quail and birds (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$), as well as between quail and brown rats (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$).

The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were significantly different between seabirds and all other potential reproductive carrion (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$). Values for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in mammals and quail did not differ between one another (Tukey's HSD: $p = 0.864$) however, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in both mammals and quail differed from $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in birds, brown rats, and sea birds (Tukey's HSD: $p < 0.01$;

$p < 0.01$; $p < 0.01$ respectively). Additionally, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in birds and brown rats were not significantly different between groups (Tukey's HSD: $p = 1.00$)

Discussion

Most burying beetle communities are characterized by a broad overlap in habitat use (Anderson 1981, Lomolino et al. 1995), and ecological opportunity such as available carrion type, success in locating carcasses, competition with other species, and breeding on a carcass can influence niche variation within and among species and may differ among habitats and over time. It is well documented that different burying beetle species exhibit preference for carcass size (Scott 1998); however, it is still unclear if individual species have resource preference beyond carcass mass (i.e. preference for small mammals or birds). Our use of stable isotope analysis will allow for identification of the species of small vertebrates used by *N. americanus* for reproduction and provide more insight into consequent feeding relationships within local assemblages of burying beetles.

Differences in carbon isotope signatures based on C_3 and C_4 crop plants can be used to study food preferences (Akamatsu et al. 2004; Feldhaar, Gebauer, and Blüthgen 2010), and feeding strategies (Trimble and Sagers 2004), whereas differences in nitrogen isotope signatures can be used to assess trophic position (Peterson and Fry 1987; Post 2002).

As expected, we detected a significant difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values among different species of wild-caught burying beetles. These differences are thought to be a result of interspecific interactions among burying beetles that influences which reproductive food resources are utilized by each species. The significantly different $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values detected in *N. americanus* suggest that the individuals in the population are relying on different carrion for reproductive feeding resources, when compared to *N. orbicollis* and *N. marginatus*. An explanation for the more positive signatures in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in *N. americanus*, may be a result of provisioning of farm raised quail for *N. americanus* pairs. The only significant difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were detected between *N. americanus* and *N. marginatus* with *N. orbicollis* falling between the other two species. This is expected, as burying beetles communities have large overlap in habitat use (Lomolino et al. 1995), but further analysis and an increased sample size is necessary to refine and support interpretations of these preliminary findings and to assess the

proportion of reproductive diet that carrion categories play in local burying beetle communities using Stable Isotope Mixing Models.

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Tables

Table 1. Wild-caught burying beetles from Nantucket Island, MA June 2017. *Nicrophorus tomentosus* was not included in the analysis due to a small sample size.

Species	N
<i>N. americanus</i>	23
<i>N. orbicollis</i>	36
<i>N. marginatus</i>	20
<i>N. tomentosus</i>	1

Table 2. Small mammal and avian species collected to determine potential carrion reproductive food source. Includes tissue type collected, sample source (Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association, Road Kill, Live Trap, Mist Net, Farm Raised), and final carrion grouping.

Species	N	Source	Tissue Type	Final Carrion Group
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	NMMA	Muscle	Brown Rats
<i>Microtus pennsylvanicus</i>	21	LT	Blood	Mammals
<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i>	22	NMMA/RK	Muscle	Mammals
<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	7	NMMA/RK	Muscle	Mammals
<i>Peromyscus leucopus</i>	12	LT	Blood	Mammals
<i>Agelaius phoeniceus</i>	2	MN	Blood	Birds
<i>Cardinalis cardinalis</i>	2	NMMA/MN	Blood	Birds
<i>Dumetella carolinensis</i>	10	NMMA/RK/MN	Muscle/Blood	Birds
<i>Turdus migratorius</i>	5	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Bombycilla cedrorum</i>	1	MN	Blood	Birds
<i>Colaptes auratus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Cyanocitta cristata</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Scolopax minor</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Larus argentatus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Sea Birds
<i>Corvus brachyrhynchos</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Catharus guttatus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>	2	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	2	NMMA	Muscle	Sea Birds
<i>Aix sponsa</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Fulica Americana</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Melanitta nigra</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Sea Birds
<i>Clangula hyemalis</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Sea Birds
<i>Somateria mollissima</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Sea Birds
<i>Tyto alba</i>	4	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	2	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	1	NMMA	Muscle	Birds
<i>Coturnix japonica</i>	4	FR	Muscle	Quail

Figures

Fig. 1. Pitfall trap sites for June 2017. Site 1 (latitude 41.2851° N, longitude -70.0523° W); Site 3 (latitude 41.3072° N, longitude -70.0009° W); Site 4 (latitude 41.2851° N, longitude -69.9926° W); Site 5 (latitude 41.2836° N, longitude -69.9780° W); Site 6 (latitude 41.2760° N, longitude -69.9891° W); Site 7 (latitude 41.2747° N, longitude -70.0124° W); Site 8 (latitude 41.2843° N, longitude -70.0215° W); Site 9 (latitude 41.2798° N, longitude -70.0314° W); Site 10 (latitude 41.2753° N, longitude -70.0009° W); Site 11 (latitude 41.2621° N, longitude -69.9884° W); Site 12 (latitude 41.2655° N, longitude -70.0320° W); Site 14 (latitude 41.2612° N, longitude -70.0478° W);

Fig. 2. Mean values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ ($\pm\text{SE}$) stable isotope signatures for vertebrate carrion and wild-caught *Nicrophorus americanus*, *Nicrophorus orbicollis*, and *Nicrophorus marginatus*. Values are given for mammal carrion (n = 54), brown rat carrion (n=7), bird carrion (n = 40), seabird carrion (n=6), and burying beetles (Table 1). Discrimination values have been added to prey items using values determined in a lab-based experiment (J. Creighton unpublished data). For all avian carrion a discrimination value of -1.0 was added for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and +3.0 was added for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$. Additionally, for all mammalian carrion a discrimination value of +0.6 was added for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and +3.0 was added for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$. Proximity of beetle signatures suggest uses of this carrion for development and growth. Given the location of sea birds in bivariate space, it is highly unlikely that they are being used by burying beetles for reproduction.

